

In-NTA curve gives a sharp inflexion in the pH range 3.0-5.5 followed by a buffer region beyond 5.5 indicating the uptake of hydroxyl ions by the primary In-NTA complex. The inflexion corresponds to the neutralisation of free acid in the In^{3+} solution and the three protons liberated due to combination of NTA with In^{3+} . The concentration of free In^{3+} ions in this pH range can be computed from the formula

$$[M] = \sqrt{\frac{C_M}{K_{\text{prac}}}}$$

where C_M is the total initial metal concentration and K_{prac} is the practical stability constant for the In-NTA complex at the desired pH. At pH=3.0 $K_{\text{prac}} = 10^8$ and hence $[M] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$. At higher pH values, K_{prac} will increase and $[M]$ will decrease further. It can be therefore assumed that in the pH range 3.0 to 5.5, indium exists exclusively as its NTA complex and separation in the titration curves in the presence of secondary ligands can safely be ascribed to the displacement of protons due to the attachment of these ligands to the primary In-NTA complex.

For secondary ligands the order of affinities is Tiron > Maltol > Kojic acid > BHA

All the secondary ligands possess two oxygen donor atoms capable of forming five membered chelate rings. Tiron contains two phenolic groups, maltol and kojic acid one each while BHA contains only an oxime group. The highest affinity of Tiron thus confirms the observation of Martell⁶ that the basic phenolate ion is the most effective co-ordinating group.

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Gravimetric Determination of Bi(III) with Morpholine-4-Carbodithioate

NEPAL SINGH, R. C. AGARWAL, V. K. MAHESHWARI
and

RAVINDRA KUMAR

Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001 (India)

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IN the present investigation, morpholine-4-carbodithioate (MCDT), a new analytical reagent has been employed for the gravimetric determination of Bi(III) in presence of several metal ions. The

reagent (MCDT) precipitates Bi(III) from bismuth nitrate solution quantitatively in the pH range 3.5 to 6.5. The complex formed, was yellow granular of composition $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_3$. The precipitate was dried at 110-120° and weighed. The chelate is thermally stable up to 200°.

Though Bayer and Ott¹ had reported morpholine-4-carbodithioate as possible analytical reagent but no systematic study has been made previously for the determination of Bi(III). In the present study an attempt has been made for the determination of Bi(III) gravimetrically in the presence of commonly occurring metal ions by means of morpholine-4-carbodithioate. The thermogravimetric analysis was also carried out with the view to know the nature of decomposition.

Experimental

Reagent: The potassium salt of the reagent was prepared by mixing potassium hydroxide, morpholine and carbon disulphide in ether at 0° in a ratio 1 : 1 : 1. The purity of the reagent was confirmed by elemental analysis and I.R. spectra. All the chemicals used were of G.R. or Analar grades of E. Merk and B.D.H. The aqueous stock solutions of reagent and bismuth nitrate were prepared in double distilled water.

Determination of Bi(III)

In a 500 ml beaker, 10 ml of 0.20M solution of bismuth nitrate and about 150 ml of distilled water were heated at 50° on a water bath. Then three fold excess of 1%(w/v) aqueous solution of the reagent was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by acetate buffer to adjust the pH in the range 3.5 to 5.5. The contents of the beaker were digested for about 30 minutes over water bath, filtered through a sintered crucible (G_4) and washed thoroughly with water. The complex was dried at 110-120° and weighed as $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_3$. The conversion factor (Bismuth/Bismuth complex) was 0.3004.

The thermolysis curve of bismuth complex had horizontal portion extending up to 180°. Above 180° it decomposes slowly upto 250°; thereafter it decomposes rapidly up to 325°. Above this temperature, again a slow decomposition occurs, and at 560°, the weight of the residue becomes constant.

Determination of Bi(III) in Presence of Foreign Ions:

A 10 ml of 0.02 M of Bi(III) solution was mixed with a known amount of foreign ion and diluted to 150 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0 by using acetate buffer. A mixture of an ammoniacal EDTA and sodium potassium tartrate solution was added to mask the Tl(I), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), In(III) and Ga(III) metal ions. In case of oxo-vanadium(IV) and oxo-titanium(IV), 1 g of sodium fluoride was added and the contents

were heated up to 50° on a water bath. The reagent solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex thus formed was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as described earlier. The ions Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , PO_4^{3-} , BO_3^{3-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ do not interfere in the gravimetric estimation of Bi(III).

Composition of the Complex: From analytical data on carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents the bismuth complex has the composition corresponds to the $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_3$ (found C, 25.72, H, 3.92 and N, 5.88 Calc. C, 25.89, N, 3.47 and N, 6.04 per cent.), where the ligand is presumably bidentate. The conductometric titrations also confirm this stoichiometry.

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Some Phenoxyacetyl Thiosemicarbazides, Substituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles, 1,2,4-Triazoles and Alkyl/Phenyl Carbamates of Substituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-Thiones

ANIL K. SEN GUPTA, O. P. BAJAJ and UMESH CHANDRA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow

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A large number of thiosemicarbazides have been reported to possess good antibacterial¹, antifungal^{2,3}, herbicidal⁴ and antiacetylcholinesterase⁵ activities. Substituted 1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles and 1, 2, 4-triazoles obtained from cyclisation of thiosemicarbazides with iodine and NaOH respectively are also known to possess similar biological activities⁶⁻¹⁰. Moreover, recently many carbamate derivatives have found world-wide application as potent insecticide^{11,12}. With this view in mind several thiosemicarbazides(I), oxadiazoles(II) and triazoles(III) carbamates(IV) have been synthesised in the laboratory to study their insecticidal and other biological properties.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Elemental

analysis (N) were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical value for all the compounds prepared.

Aryloxyacetyl hydrazines were prepared by the method of L. Conti^{1,3}.

Aryl isothiocyanates were prepared by the method of Dains^{1,4}.

1-Aryloxyacetyl-4-aryl-3-thiosemicarbazides(I)—A mixture of aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01 mole) and aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on steam bath for 2-3 hr and the solid product separated was crystallised from ethanol. The relevant data are placed in Table 1.

2-Aryloxymethyl-5-arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles(II)—were prepared according to the method of Paul and Basu^{1,5}, from the appropriate thiosemicarbazide with iodine in potassium iodide solution in presence of NaOH, and the crude solid product finally obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, the data are placed in Table 1.

3-Aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles(III)—The solution obtained by heating a mixture of compound (I, 0.01 mole) and NaOH (2N, 20 ml) under reflux for 1 hr was acidified with dilute HCl and filtered. The desired solid product after washing with water was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

3-Hydroxymethyl 5-(substituted phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones were synthesised according to the reported method^{1,6}.

Alkyl and aryl-[5-(substituted phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione-3-methyl]-carbamates(IV)—0.01 mole of 3-hydroxymethyl 5-(substituted phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione and 0.01 mole of phenyl/alkyl isocyanate were refluxed in dry benzene or dry dichloromethane-ether (50 : 50) with one drop of triethylamine for 6-10 hr. After distilling the solvent, solid residue obtained was crystallised from benzene. The compounds thus synthesised are recorded in Table 2.

Biological Activity: The compounds listed in Tables 1 and 2 were evaluated for their inhibitory effects against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus magaterium* by agar diffusion technique¹⁷. Compound Nos. 2,9,11, 12,14,16,22,27,28,31,34,36,40,41,43,44,47,49,50 and 51 inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, and Compound Nos. 2,3,5,7,9,11,13,14,16,18,20,27,30,31,32,36,38,40, 43,44,45 and 49 showed inhibition against *S. typhi*. Inhibition against *S. aureus* was observed in Compound Nos. 5,7,9,14,17,19,22,27,28,30,36,40,41,43,44 and 47. Compound Nos. 5,7,13,14,18,19,20,22,27,30, 34,36,40,43,44 and 47 showed inhibition against *B. magaterium*. Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I. Lucknow were used.